

PROJECT BOOKLET

UNITED FOR SURVEILLANCE IN EUROPE

JOIN THE MISSION TO BE BETTER PREPARED FOR FUTURE CROSS-BORDER HEALTH THREATS

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PREFACE

The COVID-19 pandemic exposed the weaknesses of European infectious disease surveillance systems when confronted with a fast-moving cross-border health threat. The lesson was unambiguous: protecting public health in the twenty-first century demands timely, digitalized, and connected systems that allow countries to detect, share, and act together.

UNITED4Surveillance was created to answer that call. Co-funded by the EU4Health program, this Joint Action brought together 40 organizations from 24 European

countries for capacity building regarding outbreak detection, hospital surveillance, and One Health surveillance at national and European level.

This booklet tells the story of what we built and learned, but it also reflects on the challenges that remain. We hope this Joint Action inspires continued collaboration towards a better prepared Europe for future infectious disease threats.

— On behalf of the UNITED4Surveillance consortium

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The UNITED4Surveillance Joint Action, co-funded by the European Union through the EU4Health programme, is a project that aimed to improve the monitoring of infectious diseases on national and European level. This project wanted to make it easier for European countries to work together and share and combine information about infectious diseases using digital tools. This is necessary to be ready for health risks from infectious diseases in the future. Together with 40 organizations from 24 European countries, the project tested and evaluated new ways for monitoring infectious diseases during outbreaks, in hospitals, and by connecting human, animal, and environmental health (One Health). The project ran from 1 January 2023 until 30 June 2026.

Important results of the project are:

- the development and testing of freely available software that can help for the detection of infectious disease outbreaks;
- updating of laboratory- and hospital systems for monitoring infectious diseases;
- creation of ways for different health organizations to share data with each other;
- improving digital infrastructure that helps to follow and report infectious diseases;
- better teamwork with important organizations, people or groups.

There are ongoing challenges with how privacy laws (GDPR) are understood and used in daily practice; whether there will be enough money to support the work in the future; and with connecting different technological systems.

The UNITED4Surveillance sustainability plan and the follow-up activities in each country (e.g. in Direct Grants) support a strong base for improved infectious disease monitoring. Also, it will help the European Union (EU) be better prepared for future health risks of infectious diseases.

INTRODUCTION & BACKGROUND

The global crisis generated by the COVID-19 outbreak revealed an urgent need for improvement in public health preparedness and pandemic response at the European level. Critical gaps and fragmentation in infectious disease surveillance systems were revealed across Europe, underscoring the need for timely, digital, and integrated systems that can respond to emerging threats and cross-border outbreaks.

The Joint Action UNITED4Surveillance contributed to implementation of the new Health Security framework under the EU regulation on serious cross-border threats to health (2022/2371) and also supported implementation of the long-term surveillance framework by the European Centre

for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) in the period 2021–2027. The project focused on integrating existing and new data sources for more comprehensive EU/EEA infectious disease surveillance, prevention and control. And by doing so, UNITED4Surveillance contributed to surveillance capacity-building within Europe and beyond, working to improve global health security.

The main objective of the Joint Action UNITED4Surveillance was to strengthen infectious disease surveillance systems at the national and European level, with improvement of integration, interoperability, and digitalization of data sources. The focus of the project was on outbreak detection, hospital surveillance, and One Health surveillance.

***“The Joint Action
UNITED4Surveillance has
been on a mission to be better
prepared for future cross-
border health threats”***

PROJECT

Consortium

UNITED4Surveillance was an EU4Health co-funded Joint Action with 40 partners from across Europe. Representing 24 countries in Europe (Figure 1), UNITED4Surveillance gathered expertise in public health, microbiology, epidemiology and data science, across the domains of public health, animal health and environmental health, thus creating a strong network of integrated surveillance for infectious disease prevention and control.

Figure 1. UNITED4Surveillance consortium

- Beneficiaries and/or Affiliated Entities
- Associated Partner

Project structure

The main activities were divided in seven Work Packages (WPs). Each Work Package had its own tasks and deliverables. *WP1* coordinated the consortium and kept an overview on the project progress and deliverables and assessing the performance of the WP objectives and activities. *WP2* focussed on outbreak detection and improving laboratory-based reporting to strengthen pandemic preparedness. *WP3* worked on integrating hospital data into infectious disease surveillance system across the EU. *WP4* dealt with One Health with the aim to integrate the infectious disease surveillance data from human, veterinary and environmental domains for proactive signaling of potential zoonotic threats. *WP5* evaluated the progress of the Joint Action to learn and improve tasks during the process. Both interim and final reports fed into *WP6* on dissemination to share the findings. *WP7* worked on sustainability of the project and its results by developing a Roadmap for the implementation of integrated infectious disease surveillance.

Project Goals

- Strengthen national and EU-level surveillance systems through digitalization, integration, and cross-sectoral collaboration.
- Pilot and evaluate innovative tools and approaches for outbreak detection, hospital-based surveillance, and One Health surveillance.
- Develop a sustainability roadmap to ensure long-term benefits and preparedness.

Infographic UNITED4Surveillance

This infographic highlights the essential components involved in strengthening integrated surveillance across Outbreak detection, One health and Hospital surveillance.

WORK PACKAGE ACTIVITIES & MAIN ACHIEVEMENTS

WORK PACKAGE 2

OUTBREAK DETECTION

OUTBREAK DETECTION

Objective

The objective of WP2 Outbreak detection was to support outbreak detection and pandemic preparedness by improving real-time surveillance for a timelier coordinated response at respectively national and European level.

This WP was divided in two main technical tasks:

Task 2.1. Improving Laboratory-based Reporting

Task 2.2. Outbreak & Signal Detection

In both tasks country-specific pilots were performed that were aligned with national priorities. Lessons learned from pilot projects were shared with other participating countries through reports, training materials and during site visits to the piloting countries.

Task 2.1. Improving Laboratory-based Reporting

Activities

- Surveys and workshops to assess needs and gaps regarding legal, technical, policy and organizational, and financial aspects in laboratory-based reporting across 23 countries.
- Country-level pilots to improve existing or develop new national platform for laboratory-based surveillance (Denmark, Finland, Norway, Netherlands).
- Workshop to develop a logical data model for a sequence database.

Main achievements and results

- **The Netherlands** (LabSentiNL/Gen-EpiX): Open-source platform for integrated genomic epidemiology, scalable for other countries.
- **Denmark:** National data transfer protocol (XRPT06 32M) revised and integrated to enable sharing of standardized data on microbial properties.
- **Finland:** New data model developed for data collection, storage and reporting of Shiga-toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC) data and integration into updated national surveillance tools.
- **Norway:** Improved reporting practices for sharing STEC data with the national level.
- **Challenges:** Legal interpretation (GDPR), technical (integration with local systems), and organizational (capacity and resources).

Task 2.2. Outbreak & Signal Detection

Activities

- Surveys to identify key gaps and requirements for implementing automated tools to detect outbreaks using routine surveillance data across 21 countries.
- Development and piloting of a Signal Detection Tool (SDT): an open-source, R-based application for automated outbreak detection, piloted in 11 EU countries.

Main achievements and results

- **Signal Detection Tool:** 63% of users reported improved daily work, increased outbreak detection accuracy, and user-friendly design.
- Training material was developed as part of the Time-Series-Analysis Module for field epidemiology (EPIET) fellows.

WORK PACKAGE 3

HOSPITAL SURVEILLANCE

HOSPITAL SURVEILLANCE

Objective

The overall aim of WP3 Hospital Surveillance was to build a foundation for timely, comparable, and representative surveillance of severe infections leading to hospitalization in each Member State.

This will be done by making an inventory and mapping all relevant health data sources for integrated surveillance of severe infections leading to hospitalization, and to assess and overcome legal and technical barriers. For Member States relying on sentinel-based approach, the objective is to establish or improve the representativeness and timeliness of surveillance, using only electronic reporting. In Member States using nation-wide register-based public health surveillance, the objective is to integrate clinical information on hospitalized patients with microbiological data.

Activities

- Country-specific surveys and a joint workshop on available surveillance system for severe infections, identification of common gaps and needs, and mapping promising health data sources.
- Country-specific pilots to establish or improve sentinel-based, electronic hospital surveillance of serious infectious diseases or syndromes (Latvia, the Netherlands, Malta, and Slovenia).
- Country-specific pilots to integrate clinical information on hospitalized patients with microbiological data (Finland, Italy, Norway, and Poland) for nation-wide register-based surveillance.
- Mapping of data flows, coding standards, technical and organizational barriers.

Main achievements and results

- **The Netherlands:** National stakeholder analysis reports, communication plan on SARI surveillance, and blueprint for SARI surveillance.
- **Slovenia and Malta:** National protocols for implementation of surveillance of severe (respiratory and gastro-intestinal) infections leading to hospitalization.
- **Latvia:** Development and implementation of a digital notification form and targeted support for use by stakeholders.
- **Finland:** New versions of the Communicable Diseases Act and Decree were drafted to allow integration of multiple register data sources for strengthened infectious disease surveillance. SARI case definitions and algorithms based on clinical ICD-10 coding and microbiological laboratory confirmation were developed and visualized in a ShinyApp application.
- **Norway:** Framework for planning and designing a nation-wide register-based surveillance system.
- **Italy:** Development of technical-operational protocol to links clinical data with microbiological data for strengthened AMR surveillance.
- **Poland:** Completed a feasibility study to improve data integration in rotavirus surveillance by mapping data sources, exploring barriers, and formulating a framework for improvements.
- Training material on hospital surveillance on the ECDC Learning Portal.

WORK PACKAGE 4

ONE HEALTH

ONE HEALTH

Objectives

Early warning surveillance at the human, animal, environmental interface is able to trigger timely public health actions and is a key pillar of effective public health surveillance for the detection of emerging pathogens and zoonoses outbreaks. The objective of WP4 One Health is to support Joint Action partners in developing One Health surveillance structures with integration of data and signals from the human, animal, and environmental domains. These efforts are intended to enhance the capability of detecting (re)emerging pathogens with zoonotic potential, perform public health risk assessments; identify the outbreak source; as well as the most effective interventions.

The work was organized around three disease groups: foodborne disease, zoonotic influenza, and vector-borne disease.

Activities

- Stakeholder analysis and systems mapping for integrated surveillance of foodborne diseases (*Salmonella*, Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC)), zoonotic influenza, and vector-borne encephalitis (West Nile virus, tick-borne diseases).
- Development and piloting of cross-sectoral data sharing platforms, early warning systems, and collaborative outbreak investigation protocols.
- Training webinars for zoonotic influenza, vector-borne disease, and foodborne disease surveillance, receiving high participant satisfaction.

Main achievements and results

- **Austria:** Established an improved *F. tularensis* case assessment process and data transfer to the national level; established zoonotic influenza surveillance in asymptomatic birds, the environment and mammals; improved cross-sectoral collaboration.
- **Belgium:** Integration of whole genome sequencing (WGS) data of human and non-human *Salmonella* isolates for surveillance; standardization *Salmonella* outbreak questionnaire; establishment surveillance of zoonotic influenza in poultry veterinarians, development protocol for management of zoonotic influenza outbreaks.
- **Netherlands:** Effectuated more effective data sharing of *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* sequence data with One Health partners; evaluation of *Salmonella* surveillance for improved cluster detection by exploring optimized sampling fraction from human and/or veterinary origin.
- **Italy:** Development and implementation of National IT platform for STEC WGS data enabled rapid cluster detection; organization of annual One Health workshops for stakeholder engagement and feedback.
- **Lithuania:** Strengthened foodborne and tick-borne encephalitis surveillance by comprehensive analysis, protocol and algorithm development; new digital tools, such as publicly available TBE maps, for information exchange and outbreak management.
- **Spain:** Developed an integrated West Nile virus surveillance programme with integrated database, simplified risk categorization tool and rapid stakeholder response protocols.
- **Denmark:** Established optimized STEC sample logistics and testing from a regional to the national reference laboratory and set up active surveillance of zoonotic influenza virus infections in humans.
- **Norway:** Improved diagnostic methods for detecting swine influenza; research on the circulation of H1N1pdm09 in swine and humans (including spillover); performed vaccinations survey; strengthened collaboration between public and veterinary health.

WORK PACKAGE 5

EVALUATION

Objective

The objective of WP5 Evaluation was to systematically assess the implementation, output, and impact of UNITED4Surveillance throughout the entire project duration. The evaluation aimed to monitor whether project activities were carried out as planned, whether participants were satisfied with project processes, and whether the Joint Action achieved its intended objectives. The evaluation framework was established at the start of the project through the Evaluation Plan (June 2023) and guided all subsequent data collection and analysis.

Activities

- Development of a structured Evaluation Plan defining methodology, indicators, and evaluation questions.
- Post-meeting surveys following each major workshop and General Assembly meeting (6 meetings evaluated, covering over 210 individual responses from up to 19 countries).
- Two annual evaluation surveys distributed to all consortium partners at the end of Year 1 (n=41, 17 countries) and Year 2 (n=28, 19 countries).
- Focus group discussion with Work Package Leaders at the General Assembly in Zandvoort (March 2024), using the ORID Discussion Method.
- Structured input collected from all Work Package Leaders for the final evaluation.
- Review of project documentation, deliverables, and milestone reports throughout the project.

Main achievements and results

- **Process evaluation:** Participant satisfaction across all evaluated meetings and workshops was consistently high, with average scores between 3.8 and 5.0 on a 1–5 scale. A positive trend was observed over time: General Assembly satisfaction scores increased from 4.27 (Zandvoort, 2024) to 4.47 (Utrecht, 2025) to 4.55

(Closing Meeting, 2026). Meeting organisation and quality of presentations were the highest-rated dimensions throughout the project.

- **Output evaluation:** Most planned deliverables and milestones were completed within the extended project timeline. Approximately 75% of survey respondents expressed satisfaction with milestone achievement in both Year 1 and Year 2. Annual surveys confirmed that the project generally adhered to planned timelines, with minor delays attributable to legal and administrative processes rather than lack of effort.
- **Outcome evaluation:** Results from the Closing Meeting survey (n=31, 17 countries) demonstrated strong project impact. The three headline figures below summarise the key outcomes as reported by participants at the end of the project:

96.7%

of respondents confirmed strengthened collaboration and exchange between countries

93.5%

found project outputs useful or very useful for their institution or country

90.3%

will continue using or building upon project outputs after the project ends

These findings were further supported by Work Package leader input, confirming that most project outputs have concrete sustainability pathways through national direct grant applications, integration into national surveillance programmes, and continuation of the expert networks established during the Joint Action.

WORK PACKAGE 6

DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION

Over the course of the Joint Action UNITED4Surveillance, over 400 communication and dissemination activities were implemented. This was not a single central activity, but a consortium-wide effort implemented through many national, professional and European communication channels. The communication and dissemination activities covered a broad mix of channels, including websites, social media, newsletters, press and media outputs, meetings, workshops, trainings, conferences, reports, scientific outputs, and through direct stakeholder engagement.

Training materials

Task 2 Signal and outbreak detection of Work Package 2 developed an open-source [Signal Detection Tool](#) and provides training material on [automated outbreak detection](#).

The Hospital Surveillance Work Package developed a webinar on [Hospital Surveillance](#) for people with a basic understanding of infectious diseases, and interest in hospital surveillance. In a 50-minute webinar several topics were addressed: the main obstacles, drivers and possible solutions of a well-functioning surveillance system; legal issues, data ownership and integration of further data sources; and ideas and use of end point definitions. The One Health Work Package developed three webinars for public health, animal health and environmental health professionals:

- Webinar [zoonotic influenza](#)
- Webinar [vector-borne diseases](#)
- Webinar [foodborne diseases](#)

UNITED4Surveillance output:

WORK PACKAGE 7

SUSTAINABILITY & ROADMAP

To ensure the long-term sustainability of UNITED4Surveillance results, the following aspects were taken into account:

- **National Sustainability Plans:** Nearly all countries in the consortium have developed or are developing formal plans, with regular monitoring, legislative review, and stakeholder engagement.
- **Funding:** Countries combine national resources and EU funding (e.g., EU4Health Direct Grants) to support sustainability, but long-term security is not yet universal.
- **Integration:** A number of countries are working on both horizontal (cross-sectoral, e.g. public health-veterinary) and vertical (local-regional-national-EU) integration, through Memorandums of Understanding (MoU's), collaboration agreements, and joint digital infrastructure projects.
- **Monitoring:** About half of countries have established indicators for sustainability (e.g., frequency of data reporting, system upgrades, stakeholder meetings, publications).
- **Risks:** Common risks identified included funding gaps, staff turnover, loss of engagement post-project, limited inter-institutional cooperation, and ongoing legal and technical barriers.
- **Best Practices:** Sharing guidelines, training materials, and regular meetings and/or webinars help maintain momentum and knowledge transfer.

All the UNITED4Surveillance results have been brought together in a user-friendly, easy accessible, and [interactive roadmap](#).

INTEGRATED RESULTS AND LESSONS LEARNED

Needs & Gaps

Outbreak Detection: Need for real-time, automated tools; improved lab-based reporting; integration of genomic data; user-friendly dashboards.

Hospital Surveillance: Need for digital, structured data; linkage of clinical and laboratory information; automation to reduce manual burden; legal clarity for data linkage.

One Health: Need for cross-sectoral data sharing platforms; regular communication and trust-building; shared surveillance targets and outbreak protocols.

Also, cross-cutting needs were identified:

- **Digitalization:** Many countries still rely on paper-based reporting or fragmented digital systems, leading to delays and data quality issues.
- **Interoperability:** Lack of common data standards (coding, classifications, technical infrastructure) prevents seamless data sharing and aggregation, both nationally and at EU level.
- **Legal Barriers:** Divergent interpretations of GDPR and unclear legal frameworks hamper data sharing, especially for sensitive health and genomic data.
- **Sustainable Funding:** Ad-hoc, project-based funding is insufficient; national and EU-level budget commitments are needed for ongoing system improvements.
- **Workforce Capacity:** Shortages of ICT and public health specialists, and the need for regular training, were identified as barriers to modernization and sustainability.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Varying levels of involvement and commitment among hospitals, laboratories, and One Health partners.

Lessons learned

- **Collaboration is Key:** Early, open, structured communication - within and across sectors - is fundamental for trust, engagement, and efficient data sharing.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Involving all relevant actors (including commercial labs and hospitals) from the start increases buy-in and success of digital integration.

- **Legal Barriers Remain:** GDPR interpretation and national legal frameworks are the most significant barriers to sustainable, cross-border, and cross-sectoral data integration.
- **Flexibility and Adaptability:** Pilots showed that adapting strategies (e.g., focus on animal rather than human surveillance when needed) is crucial to overcoming practical and legal obstacles.
- **Technical Progress:** User-friendly digital platforms, WGS, and real-time analytics significantly improved outbreak detection and response, but require ongoing training and investment.
- **Sustainability Gaps:** Many countries still lack long-term funding, permanent staff, and concrete sustainability indicators, risking loss of momentum post-project.

Challenges

- **Policy & Leadership:** There is a need for strong national and EU-level leadership to avoid fragmentation and ensure central vision and coordination.
- **Funding:** Sustained, diversified funding is essential. Reliance on project-based or ad-hoc funding undermines system resilience.
- **Legal Harmonization:** A supra-national network of legal professionals and harmonized GDPR interpretation are urgently needed. Training for public health, legal, and ICT professionals is recommended.
- **Technical Interoperability:** Standardization of data formats (ICD, LOINC, SNOMED, HL7 FHIR) and digitalization are unevenly implemented. Many systems remain paper-based or rely on local codes, impeding cross-border data exchange.
- **Data Privacy and Sharing:** There is widespread uncertainty regarding what is permitted under GDPR for sharing health/genomic data, and reluctance to share data across sectors, especially with commercial partners or for research and outbreak detection purposes.
- **Workforce and Capacity:** Insufficient ICT and data management staff, as well as lack of ongoing training, hinder the long-term operation and evolution of surveillance systems.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The Joint Action UNITED4Surveillance gathered insightful recommendations to improve integrated infectious disease surveillance and strengthen preparedness for cross-border health threats.

For Policy Makers:

- Establish permanent, cross-sectoral governance and funding mechanisms for communicable disease surveillance.
- Support a supra-national legal advisory group to harmonize GDPR interpretation and data-sharing protocols.
- Encourage ministries of health, agriculture, environment, and finance to jointly own and support surveillance infrastructure.

For Public Health Agencies:

- Invest in digitalization, interoperability, and adoption of international data standards.
- Prioritize regular training for ICT, laboratory, legal, and surveillance professionals.
- Develop stakeholder engagement strategies, including communication plans, to sustain collaboration.

For Researchers and Technical Teams:

- Embrace open-source, user-friendly platforms for outbreak detection and data sharing.
- Continue to pilot, evaluate, and adapt new digital and analytical tools (e.g., WGS, real-time dashboards).
- Document and publish lessons learned, best practices, and case studies for continuous improvement.

For the European Commission and ECDC:

- Maintain and expand funding for surveillance system upgrades, training, and One Health integration.
- Develop and disseminate EU-level legal guidance and training on data privacy, especially for genomics and cross-border data.
- Foster communities of practice and regular knowledge exchange across countries and sectors.

*“UNITED4Surveillance
has contributed to advancing
integrated infectious disease
surveillance, supporting stronger
preparedness for cross-border
health threats in the EU.”*

Ingrid Keller – DG Sante

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